

Financial Inclusion and Financial Literacy: A Study of Uttarkashi District

Deepika¹ & Diwakar Buddha²

1. Assistant Professor, Commerce, R.C.U. (Govt.) PG College Uttarkashi
Mail. ID- deepikaverma121@gmail.com, Mobile No. 8171266311
2. Head, Assistant Professor, Commerce, R.C.U. Govt. PG College Uttarkashi
Mail. ID- drbouddhadiwakar1987@gmail.com, Mobile No. 9456157054

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Abstract

India is a country with extreme diversity in its geography, history, culture and demography. This diversity of India makes difficult to suitably categorize the country on different parameters such as economic, political or demographical grounds. As we know that financial inclusion plays a vital role in the growth and development of Indian economy. Financial inclusion means including the people who are excluded from finance. This research paper focused on the objective to measure the intensity of financial inclusion and financial awareness among the people. For this paper both primary and secondary data has been used. Secondary data has taken from various annual reports of the state and primary data has been collected through structured questionnaire. For primary data collection a sample of 350 people of Uttarkashi district have taken. Study revealed that the literacy level of people about financial inclusion is very low because Uttarkashi district is a rural- urban district of Uttarakhand. The study further tells, not only should individuals of Uttarkashi district have access to basic financial services but should also enthusiastically use them. Study further concluded and recommended that there is lot more to do in this district therefore, government and financial institution should take necessary measures for the same.

Key words: Financial Inclusion, Financial Literacy, Uttarkashi, Awareness, Banks.

Financial Inclusion

Financial inclusion means that people and industries have access to financial products and services that meet their needs – credit, payments, transactions, savings, and insurance delivered in a accountable and sustainable way. The World Bank group considers financial inclusion a key enabler to diminish extreme poverty and enrichment of shared wealth. Being able to have access to operation account is a first step toward wider financial inclusion since an account allows people to store money, and send and receive payments. A transaction account serves as a gateway to other financial services, which is why ensuring that people worldwide can have access to a transaction account continues to be an area of concentration for the World Bank Group (WBG). Financial access simplifies day-to-day living, and helps families and businesses plan for everything from long-term targets to unexpected emergencies.

The COVID-19 crisis has also strengthened the need for increased digital financial inclusion. Digital financial inclusion involves the deployment of the cost-saving digital means to reach currently financially excluded and underserved populations with a range of formal financial services suited to their needs that are responsibly delivered at a cost affordable to customers and sustainable for providers.

Definition

Financial inclusion refers to efforts to make financial products and services accessible and affordable to all individuals and businesses, regardless of their personal net worth or company size. Financial

inclusion strives to remove the barriers that exclude people from participating in the financial sector and using these services to improve their lives. It is also called inclusive finance.

Financial Inclusion In India

The Reserve Bank of India has set up a commission (Khan Commission) in 2004 to look into financial inclusion and the recommendation and implementations of the commission were incorporated into the mid-term review of the policy (2005-06). In India, Financial Inclusion first featured in 2005, when it was introduced, that, too, from a pilot project in UT of Pondicherry, by K C Chakraborty, the chairman of Indian Bank. Mangalam Village turned out to be the first village in India where all households were provided banking facilities. In addition to this KYC (Know your customer) norms were stress-free for people intending to open accounts with annual deposits of less than Rs. 50,000. General Credit Cards (GCC) were issued to the poor and the disadvantaged with a view to help them access easy credit.

The government started (NMFI) National Mission for Financial Inclusion, i. e. Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) to provide universal banking and funding. According to statistical data of Uttarkashi, Commercial, Gramin & Co-Operative and post office saving banks till 2017 and performance of PMJDY in terms of accounts opened, deposits and average deposit balance till 2021 is tabulated as below:

Table. No. 1 : Commercial Banks, Gramin Banks & Co-Operative Banks:

District	In village	Within 1 km.	1-3 km.	3-5 km.	Outside 5 km.	Total
Mori	4	2	5	8	73	92
Purola	4	8	16	14	35	76
Nogaon	6	10	6	29	127	178
Dunda	7	4	15	30	69	125
Chinyalisour	3	4	7	10	74	98
Bhatwari	4	2	20	15	56	97
Total	28	30	68	106	434	666

Source: Statistics department Uttarkashi, 2017.

Note: More than one facility is available in many villages in the development blocks.

According to table no. 01, it has been revealed that there were 666 branches of different banks till 2017 in different blocks of Uttarkashi.

Table. No. 2 : Post office Saving Accounts

District	In village	Within 1 km.	1-3 km.	3-5 km.	Outside 5 km.	Total
Mori	17	11	29	29	6	92
Purola	5	10	20	21	20	76
Nogaon	27	14	27	74	37	178
Dunda	34	8	43	32	8	125
Chinyalisour	14	31	25	20	8	98
Bhatwari	25	5	38	19	10	97
Total	122	79	182	195	89	666

Source: Statistics department Uttarkashi, 2017.

According to Table No. 2, it has been revealed that there were 666 branches of post office till 2017 in different blocks of Uttarkashi.

Table. No. 3 : Tabulation of PMJDY Accounts.

S. No.	Item	March 2015	March 2016	March 2017	March 2018	March 2019	March 2020	March 2021
1	No. of PMJDY accounts opened (In Crores)	14.72	2143	28.17	31.44	35.27	38.33	42.20

2	Deposit in PMJDY (In Crores)	15670	35672	62972	78494	96107	118434	145551
3	Average Deposit per PMJDY Account (In Rs.)	1065	1665	2235	2497	2725	3090	3449
4	No. of RuPay debit cards issued to PMJDY account-holders (In Crores)	1314	1775	2199	23.65	27.91	29.30	30.90

Source: According to Ministry of Finance, 2021.

Above table shows that till 2021, 42.20 crore accounts opened in India under PMJDY and 145551 crore Rs deposited in accounts.

Statement of Problem

Financial inclusion is one of the biggest problems in front of the financial system today in rural India and infrastructural tailbacks are deteriorating it even further with each passing day. Hence the study aimed to find out the extent to which the people having different demographic profile residing in a rural area of Uttarkashi are familiar with banking habits and the study is titled as "Financial Inclusion and Financial Literacy: A Study of Uttarkashi District".

Significance of the Study

The study on financial inclusion and financial literacy among people has a great importance in today's circumstances. Active contribution of each and everyone in the financial system of the district, state and country is necessity for the effective working of financial system. Banking routine is the modest way to enter into the monetary system. So, the study proposes to analyse the intensity of financial inclusion and financial literacy among the people of Uttarkashi.

Objectives of the Study

The key objective of this study is to measure the intensity of financial inclusion and financial literacy among the people. Keeping this in view, the following specific objectives have been taken for the study.

1. To study the banking habit among people of Uttarkashi district of Uttarakhand.
2. To examine the awareness level of people about financial products and services.

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses are formulated to test under this study:

- H₁. Type of bank accounts and level of income of the respondents are independent.
 H₂. Type of bank accounts and occupational status of the respondents are Independent.
 H₃- Type of bank accounts and level of education of the respondents are independent.
 H₄- Respondents are well aware of the financial products and services provided by banking institutions.

Scope of The Study

The study revealed the intensity of financial inclusion and financial literacy among people of Uttarkashi district. The target group include government, non-government employees, unemployed/house wife, agriculturalist sand people engaged in various businesses. Banking behaviours and awareness about financial products and services come within the horizon of the study. The target group are people residing in various areas of Uttarkashi in.

Methodology

The data required for this study has collected from both primary and secondary sources. Secondary data was collected from statistical data report Uttarkashi, 2017 and report of ministry of finance, India, 2021. These sources were also used to frame questionnaire required for collecting primary data. Primary data has been collected from a sample of 350 respondents belonging to different occupational groups residing in different blocks of Uttarkashi district of Uttarakhand by administering a structured questionnaire but out of 350 only 317 people respond to questionnaire. Hypotheses 1 to 3 are tested with the help of Chi-square test of independence and the 4th hypothesis is tested with the help of Likert scaling technique and mean.

Analysis of Data

Table. No. 4: Respondents having bank accounts.

Bank accounts	Respondents	Percentage
Having bank account	300	94.63
Not having bank accounts	17	5.37
Total	317	100

Source: Primary data

The table shows that out of 317 respondents 300 people were having bank accounts and only 17 respondents do not have bank accounts.

Table. No. 5: Reason for investing in banks.

Reason	Respondents	Percentage
Credit facility	126	42.00
ATM facility	26	8.67
Location	31	10.33
Security	23	7.67
Image of the bank	25	8.33
Prompt service	11	3.67
Interest rate	43	14.34
Friends/ relatives	15	5
Total	300	100

Source: Primary data

Above table revealed that almost 42% people, majority of the respondents are of the opinion that credit facility (126 respondents) and interest rate (43 respondents) are the main reason for depositing in the Bank. 10.33% respondents and 8.67% respondents prefer location and ATM facility respectively as the reason for investing in Bank. Image of the bank, friends/ relatives and prompt services also attracted 8.33%, 5% and 3.67% respondents respectively. Above table shows that prompt service of the bank is the least preferred reason for the respondents to opening an account.

Table. No. 6: Types of bank accounts preferred by the respondents.

Bank Accounts	Respondents	Percentage
Saving bank account	206	68.67
Time Deposits	31	10.34
Recurring deposits	56	18.67
Other	7	2.33
Total	300	100

Source: Primary data, Note: One respondent can have more than one type of bank account at a time.

It has shown from the table that majority of the respondents i.e. 68.67% prefer savings bank account because of easy convenience. Followed by 18.67% of the respondents prefer Recurring Deposits. 10.34% of the respondents like to invest their funds in time deposit and 2.33% of the respondents prefer other kinds of bank accounts.

Table. No. 7: Avenues of saving other than saving bank accounts.

Avenues	Respondents	Percentage
Post office savings	106	35.33
Chit funds	16	5.33
Mutual funds	53	17.67
Life insurance	125	41.67
Total	300	100

Source: Primary data

One respondent has more than one avenue of saving other than banks at a time

From above table no. 7, it is revealed that majority of the respondents prefer life insurance (41.67) as an avenue of savings other than banks. Postoffice saving (35.33%) and mutual funds (17.67) also preferred by the respondents as savings other than banks. Only 5.33% of the respondents prefer chit funds as avenues of savings.

Table. No. 8: Financial products and services awareness among respondents.

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Very high	157	52.33
High	38	12.67
Average	68	22.67
Low	22	7.33
Very low	15	5.00
Total	300	100

Source: Primary data

It is evident from Table 8 that almost all the respondents (87.67) are aware of the financial products and services offered through the banking system. Only (12.33) percent of the respondents have below average level of awareness.

Table. No. 9

Sources of information about products and services of banking institutions.

Source	Respondents	Percentage
News papers	62	20.67
Television	81	27.00
Awareness programmes	14	4.67
Friend and relatives	25	8.33
Radio	09	3.00
From offices/ department	109	36.33
Total	300	100

Source: Primary data

The table no. 9 shows that an office (36.33%) and television (27%) are the major source of information about financial products & services and very few (3%) respondents opined about radio as a source of information about financial products and services.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES

H₁. Type of bank accounts and level of income of the respondents are independent.

Table. No. 10: Type of account and income level of respondents.

Accounts	Level of Income					Total
	Below 10000	10000-15000	15000-20000	20000-25000	Above 25000	
Saving Accounts	38	41	21	38	68	206
Time Deposits	3	9	4	8	7	31

Recurring Deposits	6	7	10	17	16	56
Other	1	1	2	1	2	7
Total	48	58	37	64	93	300

Source: Primary data

Calculated Value of Chi-Square = 0.322

Interpretation: Above table shows that the Pearson Chi Square (X^2) statistics is 0.322, and $p > 0.05$. P value (0.322) is greater than 0.05. Hence the hypothesis has accepted. i.e. type of bank accounts and level of income of the respondents are independent.

H₂. Type of bank accounts and occupational status of the respondents are Independent.

Table. No. 11

Type of bank accounts and occupational status of the respondents are Independent.

Type of Accounts	Occupational Status					Total
	Government	Private	Pensioner	Agriculture	Other	
Saving accounts	23	79	10	89	5	206
Time Deposits	15	3	9	4	0	31
Recurring Deposits	23	4	6	20	3	56
Other	3	1	1	1	1	7
Total	64	87	26	114	9	300

Source: Primary data

Calculated Value of Chi-Square = 0.000

Interpretation: Above table shows that the Pearson Chi Square (X^2) statistics is 0.000, and $p < 0.05$. P value (0.000) is smaller than 0.05. Hence the hypothesis has rejected which means type of bank accounts and occupational status of the respondents are not independent.

H₃- Type of bank accounts and level of education of the respondents are independent.

Table. No. 12: Type of bank accounts and level of education of the respondents are independent.

Type of bank accounts	Level of Education					TOTAL
	SSLC	PDC/PLUS TWO	GRADUATION	POST GRAD.	OTHER	
Saving accounts	34	38	68	57	9	206
Time deposits	2	6	12	8	3	31
Recurring deposits	16	7	8	24	1	56
Other	0	0	3	3	1	7
Total	52	51	91	92	14	300

Source: Primary data

Calculated Value of Chi-Square = 0.020

Interpretation: Above table shows that the Pearson Chi Square(X^2) statistics is 0.020, and $p < 0.05$. P value (0.171) is smaller than 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis has rejected therefore type of bank accounts and level of education of the respondents are not independent.

H₄- Respondents are well aware of the financial products and services provided by banking institutions.

Table. No. 13: Awareness level about financial products and services provided by banking institutions.

Option	Weight	Frequency	Weighted Score
Very high	1	157	785
High	2	38	152
Average	3	68	204
Low	4	22	44
Very low	5	15	15
Total	15	300	1200

Source: Primary data

Weighted mean score is 2 and mean value =3

Since the calculated mean score (2, High) is higher than the expected mean score (3), the hypothesis has been accepted. This means that the respondents have above average awareness level about the financial products and services offered through the banking system

Summary of Findings

1. Out of 350 respondents 317 respondents respond where 300 respondents have bank account and only 17 respondents have not bank account
2. Majority of the respondents are of the opinion that credit facility (42%), Interest rate (14.34%) and bank ATM facility (8.67%) are the main reason for depositing in the Bank. Only (3.67%) respondents prefer prompt service as the reason for investing in Bank.
3. Easiness of credit access, large no: of schemes and performance record are the most preferred factors that attracted customers towards banks. Though large no: of scheme is the main factor which there respondents give first preference, a greater number of respondents prefers easiness of access as the main factor in selecting bank.
4. Through the analysis the majority of the respondents (68.67%) prefer Savings Bank Account because of easy convenience. Followed by (18.67%) of the respondents prefer Recurring Deposits. (10.34%) of the respondents like to invest their funds in Time deposit and (2.33%) of the respondents prefer other kinds of deposit schemes.
5. From the analysis it is found that majority of the respondents prefer Life insurance as an avenue of savings other than banks. (41.67%) respondents prefer Life insurance as an investment. Post office saving (35.33%) also preferred by the respondents as savings other than banks. Only (5.23%) of the respondents prefer chit funds as avenues of savings.
6. The analysis found that office and colleague (36.33) and television (27%) are the major source of information about financial products and services. Newspaper (20.67) also provides information about financial products and services to a certain extent. Only 3% of the respondents opined about radio as a source of information about financial products and services.
7. Almost (52.33%) respondents are aware about the facilities and schemes given by several banks. Their awareness level is very high. Then, (12.67%) respondents are highly aware, (22.67%) respondents are having average knowledge, (7.33%) having low knowledge about banking rest of the respondents (10.45%) are having having very low knowledge about banking facilities and banking schemes.

8. According to data analysis it is found that 1st and 4th hypotheses have been accepted and 2nd and 3rd hypotheses have been rejected.

Conclusions

A great change has occurred in the last ten years to overcome financial exclusion. An outline of policy has emerged from a comprehensive process of discussion and debate. Initiatives and investigational schemes have been launched to put the policies into effect. we cannot become satisfied and become victims of our own success. Not only should individuals have access to basic financial services and facilities but should also enthusiastically use them. Financial inclusion is more important after the ear of Covid-19 pandemic. It must be essential part of today's life as accountholders or people are more likely to use various financial services, such as credit and insurance, to start and expand businesses, invest in education or health, manage risk, and weather financial shocks, which can improve the overall quality of their lives. Uttarkashi is hilly district of Uttarakhand and most of the blocks of the Uttarkashi comes under rural and urban areas. Uttarkashi has done very good in financial inclusion but there still a lot more to do: stimulating use of monetary services as well as access; ensuring long-term sustainability of current efforts and handling new forms of exclusion and down grade as they arise.

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